

Synthesis of some lanthanide(III) complexes derived from 4-[N-(4-methoxybenzylidene)amino]antipyrinethiosemicarbazone

R. K. Agarwal*, (Ms.) Neetu Goel and Alok Kumar Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai Post-Graduate College, Sahibabad-201 005, India

Manuscript received 31 August 1999, revised 29 May 2000, accepted 26 August 2000

Lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes of 4-[N-(4-methoxybenzylidene)amino]antipyrinethiosemicarbazone (MBAAPTS) with the general composition $\text{Ln}(\text{MBAAPTS})(\text{NO}_3)_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy or Ho}$) have been synthesized. The complexes are non-ionic. The NO_3^- are bidentate while MBAAPTS is tridentate (NNS) ligand. Magnetic, spectral and thermal properties of the complexes have also been investigated.

The complexing ability of antipyrine has been modified by the preparation of Schiff base derivatives¹. In continuation of our studies on a series of biologically potential thiosemicarbazones derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and its metal complexes^{2,3}, we report here the lanthanide nitrate complexes of 4-[N-(4-methoxybenzylidene)amino]antipyrine thiosemicarbazone (MBAAPTS).

Results and Discussion

The reactions of lanthanide nitrate with MBAAPTS result complexes of the general composition $\text{Ln}(\text{MBAAPTS})(\text{NO}_3)_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy or Ho}$). The complexes are generally stable and could be stored for a long time. The low molar conductance values of the complexes in nitrobenzene ($3.2\text{--}4.1 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) reveal their non-electrolytic nature⁴. The ratio of molecular weight observed to that calculated (*ca.* 0.98) shows that the complexes are monomeric in solution (in nitrobenzene).

The magnetic moment value of the La complex reveals its diamagnetic nature. The values of complexes of Pr (3.67), Nd (3.58), Sm (1.64), Gd (7.89), Tb (9.28), Dy (10.53) and Ho (10.29 B.M.) show their paramagnetic nature due to the presence of *4f*-electrons, which are effectively shielded by *5s*²*5p*⁶ electrons. The magnetic moments of the complexes are within the range predicted and ob-

served in the compounds of paramagnetic ions as reported earlier⁵.

Infrared spectra : The strong ligand bands observed at 3420 and 3310 cm^{-1} (NH) remained unaffected after complexation. The ligand band at 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N of imine nitrogen)⁶ shifted to lower wavenumbers on complexation, suggesting involvement of unsaturated nitrogen atoms of the two azomethine groups in bonding with the metal ion. Other bands observed at 1320, 1195, 1120, 1095; 840, 820 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=S}} + \nu_{\text{C=N}} + \nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\delta_{\text{N-C-S}} + \delta_{\text{C=S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ modes, respectively⁷. Coordination of sulfur with the metal ion would result in the displacement of electrons towards the latter, thus resulting in the weakening of C=S bond. Hence, on complexation C=S stretching vibrations should decrease and that of CN should increase⁸. In the present complexes, the bands at 1320 and 1195 cm^{-1} increased by 50–60 cm^{-1} . Bending modes of N–C–S and C=S also increased but to lesser extent. On the other hand, on complexation the bands at 840, 820 cm^{-1} shifted to lower wavenumbers with reduced intensity. All these changes precludes any unambiguous ascertain of metal-sulfur bond. The possibility of thione-thiol tautomerism in this ligand has been ruled out since no band around 2700–2560 cm^{-1} occurs in the spectra of the complexes⁹. In far-IR region, $\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ln-S}}$ were also assigned¹⁰. Hence, the ligand behaves as neutral tridentate group and the metal ions are coordinated through N and N of two azomethine group and of S of thio-keto group.

The spectra for NO_3^- absorption in $[\text{Ln}(\text{MBAAPTS})-(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ complexes revealing two strong absorptions at 1525–1485 and 1300–1280 cm^{-1} are attributed to ν_4 and ν_1 modes of vibration of the covalently bonded nitrate group.

respectively, suggesting that the nitrate group are inside the coordination sphere^{11,12}. Other absorptions associated with the covalent nitrate groups are also observed in the spectra of the complexes. The ($\nu_4 - \nu_1$) difference of $\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for these complexes suggests strong covalency for the metal-nitrate bonding. To identify the monodentate or bidentate nature, we applied Lever separation method¹³. A separation of $\sim 30\text{--}40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ($\nu_1 + \nu_4$) bands in the $1800\text{--}1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region concludes the bidentate nitrate coordination. The bidentate character of nitrate groups has been established by X-ray¹⁴ and neutron diffraction studies¹⁵. Hence, the nitrate groups in the present complexes are of bidentate nature¹⁶.

Electronic spectra : Lanthanum(III) has no significant absorption in the visible region. The absorption bands of Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} and Ho^{III} in the visible and near-IR region appear due to transitions from the ground levels 3H_4 , $^4I_{9/2}$, $^4H_{5/2}$ and 5I_8 to the excited J -levels of $4f^n$ -configuration, respectively. Some red-shift or nephelauxetic effect is observed in acetonitrile solution of these coordination compounds. The red-shift of the hypersensitive bands has been utilised to calculate the nephelauxetic effect (β) in these chelate complexes. From the β -values the covalence factor ($b^{1/2}$), Sinha parameter ($\delta\%$) (metal-ligand covalency, percent) and the covalency angular overlap parameter (η) have been calculated¹⁷. The positive values for $(1-\beta)$ (0.0023–0.0125) and $\delta\%$ (0.2325–1.2658) in these compounds suggest that the bonding between the metal and the ligand is covalent compared with the bonding between the metal and an aquo ion. The values of bonding ($b^{1/2}$) (0.0340–0.0895) and angular overlap parameter (η) (0.0011–0.0081) parameters were found to be positive indicating covalent bonding.

Thermogravimetry : The pyrolysis curves of the complexes reveal the non-hygroscopic nature of the complexes. At $\sim 265^\circ$, the complexes start to lose mass with partial evaporation of the organic ligand. About 0.5 molecule of MBAAPTS is lost at $265\text{--}330^\circ$ (26.26–27.16%), and in the range $355\text{--}395^\circ$, a loss of 52.82–54.29% is observed because of the complete loss of the organic ligand. The residues obtained after heating at 835° to constant weight is very close to that expected for the lanthanide oxide¹⁸.

The conductance data indicate the non-ionic nature of the complexes. Hence all the three NO_3^- ions are present inside the coordination sphere. IR data reveal the bidentate nature of the NO_3^- . Thus lanthanide ions are surrounded by six oxygen atoms from three bidentate nitrate ions, two nitrogen and one sulfur atom of MBAAPTS and thus providing coordination number of nine for the lanthanide

metal.

Experimental

The lanthanide nitrates (Rare Earth Products Ltd., India) were used as such. The ligand MBAAPTS was synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrine by the reported method².

All the complexes were prepared by the following method. The corresponding lanthanide nitrate (1 mmol) and MBAAPTS (1.1 mmol) dissolved separately in hot ethanol (15 ml each) were mixed and refluxed for $\sim 3 \text{ h}$. The resulting solution was concentrated to 10 ml and to this diethyl ether (15 ml) was added with vigorous stirring. The resulting finely divided solid mass was washed with diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} .

The chemical analyses and physicochemical studies of the complexes were performed as reported earlier^{1–3}.

References

1. R. K. Agarwal and R. K. Sarin, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1993, **67**, 1207; *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1994, **24**, 185; R. K. Agarwal and H. Agarwal, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 715; R. K. Agarwal, H. Agarwal and A. K. Manglik, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1966, **26**, 1163.
2. R. K. Agarwal, B. Bhushan and G. Singh, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1993, **65**, 131.
3. R. K. Agarwal, G. Singh and B. Bhushan, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1994, **68**, 871; R. K. Agarwal, H. Agarwal and I. Chakraborti, *Qatar. Univ. Sci. J.*, 1994, **14**, 92.
4. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 110.
5. A. K. Srivastava and V. B. Rana, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 723; A. K. Srivastava, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, communicated.
6. G. Shankar, R. R. P. Kumar and S. K. Ramalingam, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 991; G. S. Devi and P. Indrasenan, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987 **133**, 157.
7. K. Swaminathan and H. M. N. H. Irving, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1291.
8. J. E. Stewart, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **26**, 1291; V. B. Rana, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1826.
9. P. W. Sadler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 957.
10. D. M. Adam, "Metal-Ligand and Related Vibrations", Edward Arnold, London, 1967.
11. J. R. Ferraro, *J. Mol. Spectra*, 1960, **4**, 99.
12. C. C. Addison and N. Logan, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1964, **6**, 95.
13. A. B. P. Lever, E. Mantiovani and B. S. Ramaswamy, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, **49**, 1957.
14. T. Ueki, A. Zalkin and D. Templeton, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1966, **20**, 842.
15. J. C. Taylor, M. H. Mueller and R. L. Hitterman, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1966, **20**, 842; J. I. Bullock, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **29**, 2257.
16. S. K. Madan and A. M. Donohue, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **20**, 842.
17. S. P. Sinha, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, **22**, 57; S. P. Tandon and P. C. Mehta, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1970, **52**, 4313.
18. R. K. Agarwal and S. K. Gupta, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1985, **95**, 99.